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PRODUCTION OF PRESENCE: 1926/2026

In 2026, the world will celebrate the 100th anniversary of the births of M. Foucault and D. Attenborough, as well as the publication of the first Winnie-the-Pooh book [8].

What was it like, the year 1926? The answer to this question is H. U. Gumbrecht's book *In 1926 Living on the Edge of Time* [4]. For his historiographical experiment, the author chose the year randomly and also cautioned that at the time of selection, this date «[not] anticipates any forthcoming public anniversary» [4, p. 426]. Therefore, when a 100-year rhyme to this date appears just as coincidentally, it is possible to immerse oneself in the atmosphere of 1926 without reservation in order to identify other parallels and rhymes to the year 2026.

For instance, the atmosphere of 1926 gives the impression of a «humming» year of automobiles [4, p. 26–33], which is unlikely to surprise an average city dweller of 2026 (the absence of difference would not have surprised the author either [4, p. xi]). Danger and fear, of which the automobile had once been a symbol [4, p. 28], have given way to a perception of the car as something commonplace and associated with prosperity [4, p. 29–31]. In the book *After 1945: Latency as Origin of the Present*, H. U. Gumbrecht recalls his father's and grandfather's Opels in post-war Germany precisely as features of general prosperity [6, p. 1–3; 116–177]. Having become safe, automobiles play such a role in 2026 as well.

Although biplane airplanes [4, p. 3–11] have become a rarity in 2026, Americans [4, p. 12–21] are still flooding Paris— perhaps even more so than in 1926: 350 thousand versus 5 million [2], a 14-fold increase during this period.

The list could be continued, but overall, at the level of presence, 1926 and 2026 share a strange, common anxiety and eventfulness. Even a skeptical remark concerning significant technological progress does not, in reality, distinguish them [4, p. 241–249]. It is worth emphasizing once again that, in the sense that it is possible to be present in the year 1926 and (if it is also possible) to be present in the year 2026, the similarity between these years, separated by a century, becomes noticeable.

Undoubtedly, one of M. Foucault's most frequently used ideas in H. U. Gumbrecht's academic works is the idea of the «crisis of representation» [3, p. 5; 5, p. 37–38; 7, p. 30–31]. An interesting question arises in light of the rapprochement between the years 1926 and 2026: is it possible to overcome the crisis of representation (especially the crisis of historical representation) precisely through the «presentation» of historical worlds, instead of their «representation» [7, p. 322]? That is to say, can the potential experience of making present and drawing closer the historical worlds of 1926 and 2026 offer a successful solution to the problem of the crisis of representation—which reveals itself in a radical multiplicity of perspectives on the phenomenon under study and the impossibility of attaining «reliable» knowledge of the past (and present) as such? And what type of knowledge do we acquire through the experience of making present the worlds of 1926/2026?

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